

The ESO Reticon[®] System: a detector for the far red* with the B&C spectrographs (short manual and first results)

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Accessibility of the far red range, roughly redwards of 750nm, was limited until recently by the low quantum efficiency of the S1 photocathodes, the only ones capable to reach the 1 μ m region. Indeed, the few instruments designed to reach as far with S1 photomultipliers, like the Lick scanner, or the Oke multichannel spectrometer, required the collecting area of large telescopes to gather significant results. The availability of Silicon detectors, which reach peak responsive quantum efficiency above 70% in the 700-900 nm range, now changes the situation. Furthermore, as such detectors can be built in arrays of significant size, either linear or two dimensional, without dead space between pixels, one gains the multiplex advantage over the use of single photomultipliers.

These arguments have led us, at ESO, to construct a simple, easy-to-handle device based on a self-scanned silicon photodiode array as detector for low-dispersion spectroscopy in the red, at a time where CCD's were not available for such applications. Such self-scanned arrays have the great disadvantage over CCD's of a much larger read-out noise (typically 800-1000 e⁻ r.m.s), but as their use was initially confined to high-resolution, high signal-to-noise spectroscopy (Vogt et al. 1978), the large number of photons required ensured that the photon noise was largely dominating the read-out noise. But a simple exposure time calculation shows that, with the collecting area of a large telescope like the ESO 3.6m, much interesting work can also be done at low dispersion in the relatively

*based on ESO technical note IDG 120-79 (1979) and on a draft, unpublished Messenger article (1983)

unexplored region redwards of 700nm during bright time, still with good signal to noise ratio. The large number of pixels of the silicon diode array manufactured by Reticon[®] Corporation (up to 1872) and a large effective area of a single pixel (25 x 430 μm) gives it some specific advantages for low dispersion spectroscopy on single or extended objects. While there is no doubt that, in the future, progress in CCD's might do better than Reticon's, some of the observational problems in this spectral range will be common to both detectors. We therefore describe below some of the experience gained with the ESO Reticon system which is in routine use since end of 1979. Section II describes the instrument and its properties, while Section III is devoted to observations, calibration and reduction procedures. In section IV, we present a selection of scientific results obtained with this instrument, prefiguration of what will be achievable with higher performance detectors in the future.

II The instrument and its performances

The spectrograph used is the standard Boller & Chivens spectrograph mounted at the f/8 Cassegrain focus of the 3.6m telescope (or also at the f/15 Cass focus of the 1.52m). The scale at the detector level is 26 μm per second of arc and available gratings provide dispersions ranging from 58 up to 450 $\text{\AA}/\text{mm}$ in the red. The detector is a Reticon[®] 1024 C/17 dual array, consisting of two individual arrays of 1024 elements each, placed on the same substrate. Each diode has a width of 25.4 μm and a height of 432 μm , the separation between the two parallel arrays being of 2.44mm (Zurbuchen, 1978). Two independent spectra can therefore be recorded simultaneously, usually one for the object, and one for the sky, the corresponding apertures being defined by a decenter located just above the slit. At the 3.6m telescope, this corresponds to a separation of 94'' between object and sky, for a maximum aperture around 16''. Adequate sampling is achieved with a 2'' slit. The same set-up (spectrograph + detector) can also be used at the 1.52m telescope, where separation between object and sky is then 220''. Alignment problems are minimized by having the detector permanently mounted on a dedicated spectrograph-camera, optimized for work at 1 μm , which can then easily replace the one used for classical work in the visible range.

The way a p-n junction photodiode works in a photon integrating mode can be simply assimilated to a capacitance, initially reverse biased to 5V, and slowly discharged by the electrons-holes pairs generated by the incoming light, and by the thermal generation. At the end of the integration, the charge necessary to reach again 5V is measured successively for each diode and converted to a digital signal stored in the computer. Two perturbing effects are associated to this sequence: a fixed pattern signal (erroneously called "fixed pattern noise") due to the clock driver sequence (necessary to connect successively each pixel to the output video line) is superposed to the useful signal; and the system has an overall read-out noise. The fixed pattern signal can be removed entirely by subtracting a zero exposure taken immediately after the object exposure, and subtracts well provided the electronics and temperature are very stable. The read-out noise is dominated by the pre-

amplifier noise, which is directly proportional to the total number of diodes connected to a single video line. Usually, all the pixels are connected to a single line, which explains the high read-out noise (typically 800-1000 e⁻ for a 1024 array), or at most to two output lines, with then the additional problem of gain differences between the two lines, which can however be corrected by adequate flat fielding.

The electronics and set-up of our system has essentially followed the precepts of Vogt et al. (1978) and is described in details in Dennefeld et al. (1979). The system's gain has been adjusted such as to have one unit of the 12 bits of the Analog to Digital converter (ADU's) corresponding to the 2 ms readout noise. The saturation of the AD converter then occurs for a total charge corresponding to only 24% of the saturation charge in an individual diode*. Over this range, the linearity has been measured for each diode, and no deviation larger than 0.58% (for the worst diode) was found. With this set-up, the theoretical dynamical range is then of 4000, slightly less in practice because the fixed-pattern signal itself occupies about 300 ADU's.

The detector is mounted in a cryostat with liquid nitrogen cooling, where the temperature is controlled and regulated to better than half a degree. The temperature can be varied in the range of -70° to -150°C and at any working temperature below -80°C, the cryostat requires at most one refilling during a 12h hours observing night. The working temperature can be chosen by the observer, depending on the observing program, as a trade-off between two opposite effects: the dark current decreases rapidly with temperature (see Fig. 1), allowing longer exposures to be taken, but the red response also decreases with temperature. Fig. 2 shows that, between -80° and -120°C, almost a factor of 2 in quantum efficiency is lost at, or longwards of, 1µm wavelength and work in this far red range should obviously be done at as high a temperature as possible. The problem is similar with modern CCD's and is often neglected for operating convenience reasons. Here, the best trade-off for routine work has been found around -110°C, where the dark current is then negligible with respect to the sky background.

*Today, one would obviously rather use a 16 bit analog to digital converter, not available at the time....

The relative spectral response of the whole system has been evaluated by observations of standard stars. As an example, with a 300 l/mm grating blazed at 900nm (standard catalogue grating) and giving a dispersion of 228 Å/mm, the efficiency peaks around 770nm. The working angle of the grating was chosen slightly bluewards of its blaze angle, to allow coverage of the full available spectral range (~ 600-1100 nm) without overlapping orders. If necessary, one can get a slightly better efficiency in the far red by changing the grating, but then at the expense of losing part of the blue side. The absolute efficiency, measured with standard stars and wide opened slit in good transparency conditions, gives 0.08 (atmosphere + telescope + spectrograph + detector) at peak (770 nm) with the above described set-up (uncertainty 20% due to uncertainty in the seeing value). The same measure made for the Image Dissector Scanner, with the same spectrograph, gives 0.02 at 500 nm. After correcting for the respective grating efficiencies (measured in laboratory), the ratio of the two results is in excellent agreement with the ratio of quantum efficiencies of Silicon to an S20 photocathode. From there on, it is easy to calculate the S/N obtained in a given exposure time with the standard formula.

III Observations and reductions

The electronics is controlled by software installed in a Motorola 6800 processor, allowing complete off-line checks and adjustments. It also serves as an interface between the instrument and the main computer, from which the observer controls both the detector and the spectrograph parameters in normal operations. It is integrated within the standard ESO Image Handling and Processing (IHAP) software. Once a start command has been given, the system automatically executes a series of five read-outs to properly recharge the capacitances before integration on an object; it also ensures that a given file/observation is not closed before at least one zero-integration with closed shutter has been taken at the end, to allow a clean subtraction of the fixed pattern signal (FPS).

Pixel to pixel variations, and differences in gain between the two amplifiers (even- and odd- diodes are read by two different videolines) have to be corrected via Flat Field exposures taken during day time. When working over a large spectral range (as in the

example described above), the illumination of the FF lamp is far from flat, and these exposures have therefore to be flattened out, before pixel-to-pixel variations can be corrected out. Wavelength calibration is done via exposures from a He-Ar or He-Ne lamp, and the dispersion curve is well approximated by a third- or fifth-order polynomial, with standard deviation of less than 0.3\AA at $228\text{\AA}/\text{mm}$, that is less than a fraction of a pixel.

The mean extinction curve for LaSilla is derived from the measurements of Tüg (1980) but extends only out to 880nm. A small extrapolation is thus necessary to go out to $\sim 1.1\mu\text{m}$, and will be measured later, but the differential extinction is anyway small in this region. More important in this spectral region are the various atmospheric absorption bands, due to either molecular oxygen or to water vapour, and strongly dependant on airmass: a good correction of them will require observation of standard stars at an airmass similar to the one of the science object. In view of the complex structure of those bands, observations at higher spectral resolution might be necessary, if lines of interest are falling directly within the atmospheric bands, as shown for example by Dennefeld & Stasinska (1983) for the specific case of the [SIII] 9532\AA line.

The overall response curve of the system is determined through observations of standard stars. However, at the time observations started with this system, few standard stars were available with measurements extending to at least 10800\AA . This was undoubtedly due to the previous lack of detectors with adequate response out to the far red, and we found a few suitable stars only in Oke (1964), or Hayes (1970). All these stars were measured with scanner instruments and photomultipliers as detectors, over large bandwidths (30 to 50\AA), thus providing only about 15 photometric points over the whole Reticon spectral range ($5800\text{-}10800\text{\AA}$). The response curve is thus well determined only in the regions where the changes are smooth, and less so around regions with abrupt changes (like the Paschen jump) or close to atmospheric absorption bands (because of the large bandwidth of the standard measurements). Some improvements are planned by adding more points to the standards, either by fitting a theoretical continuum to the existing photometric observations and interpolating, or/and by using specific Reticon observations in addition. A greater number of secondary or tertiary standards has become recently available thanks to the work of Johnson (1980) and Cochran (1981), but still not extending further than 10200\AA . For work beyond $1\mu\text{m}$, the table of absolute fluxes should thus be prepared by combining the more recent data with the older ones of Oke or Hayes for specific standard stars, until the new Reticon data will provide a homogeneous set of points. In view of the rapidly dropping responsivity redwards of $1\mu\text{m}$, observations of the standards will anyway require at least two exposures, a deep one to get sufficient S/N in the far red, and a shorter one in the bluer part of the spectrum which saturates in the deep exposure. In any case, it is crucial to pay great attention to the choice of the standard star(s) to be observed, to make sure that the available photometric data do indeed extend far enough into the red for the science objectives.

The region redwards of $H\alpha$ is dominated by night-sky emission, most notably the vibration-rotation bands from the hydroxyle (OH) radical. Fig.4 shows a low-dispersion ($228\text{\AA}/\text{mm}$) spectrum of the night-sky emission obtained with the Reticon system in one hour

exposure. The principle features are identified, and precise wavelengths can be found in Hubbard et al. (1980). Besides OH, the only other, strong emission is the (0,1) band of O₂ at 8629.8Å. The (0,2) O₂ band at 9965Å is confused with the (9,5) OH band. The fact that no strong emissions are seen here redwards of ~10400Å simply reflects the drop in sensitivity of the system with this setting. ** Note that one of the strongest lines of interest in this spectral range, the HeI 10830Å line, is almost exactly superposed with the head of the Q branch of the (5,2) OH band, so that a good sky subtraction is absolutely essential. This OH emission is essentially variable, with daily and seasonal patterns. The OH radical is formed by reaction of ozone onto atomic hydrogen under solar radiation at the top of the mesosphere. From long term monitoring of OH emission at Haute-Provence Observatory in France (e.g. Berthier 1956), it has become clear that the OH emission is decreasing steadily following sunset (by a factor of two or more) but then increases again in the second half of the night. Observers are therefore advised to observe their faintest objects around the middle of the night rather than just after twilight. The seasonal behavior indicates a maximum of emission around October-December (similar to what is observed at OHP), but the sampling is too irregular at this stage to be able to give good statistics.

The S/N obtained in a given exposure can easily be calculated with the standard formula (not reproduced here) and is still read-out noise limited (marginally so, due to the strong sky emission) for low dispersion, low S/N exposures. This will not be true anymore with the first CCD's whose r.o.n. is less than 100 e⁻ rms, but then the dominant noise source will be the sky emission. The observing technique has thus to allow a good sky subtraction afterwards. Using the two, parallel series of diodes (1024 pixels each), one will record the object, and the other the sky (except for extended objects). The simultaneous recording of object and sky should thus allow a good sky subtraction, insensitive to temporal variations...except that the two arrays are different in mechanical alignment, absolute sensitivity and electronic parameters. A full, independent calibration (flat fielding,

** Since then, the generalized use of CCD's in the red, and HgCdTe detectors in the near-IR, has amply demonstrated the strength (and nuisance) of night-sky OH bands.

wavelength calibration, response curve) of each array should therefore be implemented, with the corresponding degradation of the signal to noise ratio, before the sky subtraction can be made. It has been found adequate, in practice, as a compromise, and as long as sky variations are minimal, to split long exposures in two parts, the object being alternately observed in each of the two channels. This allows a clean sky subtraction pixel by pixel, in the same array, before any absolute calibration. The technique is similar to the one used with the Image Dissector Scanner in the visible, simply is more sensitive here to possible sky variations due to the longer exposures needed in this domain. The practical observing sequence proposed for faint object work is thus the following: first a “dark” exposure to record the fixed pattern signal, then first integration on object, second integration with the object in the other channel, and a final “dark” exposure followed by a wavelength calibration. For integrations of half an hour or more, it has been found convenient to also record a fixed-pattern signal with a “dark” exposure in-between the two object integrations, to allow monitoring of eventual electronic instabilities. We have found so far no problems in integrating for one hour or more in each channel. The next section will show some scientific results obtained this way.

IV Some scientific results

This detector, attached to the B&C Cassegrain spectrographs both at the 3.60m and at the 1.52m telescope, was extensively used to explore this far-red region of the spectrum, on many different types of objects. As a first example, we show its use for refined abundances determinations. In gaseous nebulae, be it HII regions, Planetary Nebulae (PNe), or Supernova-Remnants (SNR), the abundance of a given element is derived from the ion observed in the visible range, and empirical corrections have to be made for the other ionization stages from the same element but not observable in the optical. Observations of more ionization levels, by extending the observed spectral range, are therefore important to improve the accuracy of abundances determinations. A good example is Sulfur: the only lines available in the visible are the weak 6717-6731Å [SII] doublet from S^+ (or eventually the even weaker blue 4070Å one), useful for electronic density determinations, but representing a marginal contribution to the total S abundance. Indeed, in HII regions at least, the dominant element is S^{++} , from which come the [SIII] lines at 9069-9532Å. These lines can now be observed with our new system, and a better S abundance derived: Dennefeld & Stasinska (1983) have thus shown that the S/O ratio was nearly the same in all HII regions observed in our Galaxy and in the Magellanic Clouds, close to the solar value, and compatible with a production in massive stars. For PNe, the dominant ion is S^{3+} , whose lines fall in the near-IR, and as a result, even with the [SIII] lines, their S abundance is still less reliable. For SNR's, the dominant element is S^+ , and the [SII] lines stronger (e.g. Dennefeld (1982) for illustrative spectra), but the excitation is different and the interpretation is model dependant. Fig.4 shows an example of spectra obtained with the

Reticon detector for each of the three types of nebulae, and the changes in the [SIII]/[SII] line ratio is readily visible.

In Fig.5, two emission line stars are presented. In the case of the symbiotic star RR Tel, it is obvious that access to the far red immediately reveals the presence of the red companion through

its characteristic absorption bands. For a nova, emission lines are dominant, mainly Paschen lines, but the details of course depend on the observed phase after the explosion. Many other stars show emission lines, particularly the red Calcium triplet (like TTauri) but are not illustrated here. A full MK standard atlas in this spectral region has been observed with the 1.52m telescope (except for a few, fainter stars observed with the 3.6m), including emission line stars, and is in preparation***. A sample of southern WR stars is presented in Vreux et al. (1983).

*** Now published as Danks & Dennefeld (1994)

In the extragalactic domain, a few Seyfert galaxies or QSO's have been observed as tests, and are presented in Fig. 6. Noteworthy are some FeII multiplets, often seen also in Narrow-line Seyfert 1 galaxies, and the OI line at 8446Å which could be used in diagnostic diagrams. For high-redshift objects, the H α line could be observed up to $z \approx 0.6$, while Ly α should be detectable up to $z \approx 8$. Study of such high-redshift objects will certainly benefit from access to this far-red domain, particularly with the 3.6m telescope and the availability of modern CCD's with lower read-out noise.

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